

ISic4427

Inscribed boundary stone

Language

Latin

Type

terminus

Material

volcanic

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe

Autopsy

none

Last Change

2020-07-01 - Jonathan Prag created the file from published information

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Paternò

Provenance

The only record is in the manuscript collection of Gaetano Marini, whence later editions. Marini records it as being found in the 'ager Catinensis', in the locale known as 'le Timpe', and in his time preserved in front of the church of the village of Sferri

Coordinates

37.501100, 14.796780

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, lost

Physical Description

Not directly described by Marini, but the use of 'item' after an initial description of a quadrangular column of volcanic stone, with reference to ISic4425, suggests the same form

Dimensions

Height not recorded cm

Width not recorded cm

Depth not recorded cm

Layout

The text is recorded on a single line, beneath a plain cross

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

No information is preserved

Letter heights:

Line 1: not recorded mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. +

2. EKL KAT NUA

Apparatus

Text from Marini

Pace omits the cross and splits the text across three lines

Pace, Ferrua: ECL

Translation

Commentary

The text of this inscription appears to be written in Latin letters (in other comparable examples such as ISic1404 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1404>] the letters appear either to be Greek or a mixture; cf. ISic1338 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1338>] , ISic4424 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4424>] , ISic4425 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4425>] , ISic4426 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic4426>]). Nonetheless the presence of variations on the formulation of $\bar{\epsilon}\bar{\kappa}\bar{\lambda}$ KAT which is found also in those texts, and the broadly similar geographical area of origin, strongly suggest that this stone has a similar context, namely as a boundary stone relating to the lands of the early church in Sicily. Like Pace before him, Ferrua interpreted these in this way, and expands this text speculatively as: ek(k)l(esiae) Kat(inensis) n(o)va(le). This text, together with ISic4425 and ISic4426, is only reported by Gaetano Marini, and the texts in Angelo Mai, Pace, and Ferrua all derive directly from this one record. Pace understood Marini to refer to four sides of a single stone, but Ferrua more reasonably interprets the annotations of Marini to refer firstly to two sides of one stone (ISic4425: 'hinc', 'inde'); and then to two further separate texts (ISic4426: 'item altera reperta in agro'(?)) and in this case: 'item altera inscripta'. It is not impossible that this text and ISic4426 are in fact the same as the two recorded by Gualtherus (ISic1338 and ISic4424), but the differences, especially in this case, are sufficient to suggest not.

The date of the stone is very difficult to ascertain. If the interpretation suggested by Ferrua is adopted, making this one of several boundary markers for church property from the wider area of the Catania hinterland, then a date of the fifth century AD or later seems likely. It would be possible to accept the reading of KAT as referring to Catania, without accepting the need to interpret ECL or EKL as a reference to the church.

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

- Pace, B. 1949. *Arte e civiltà della Sicilia antica*. Volume quarto. Barbari e Bizantini. Rome, Naples, Città di Castello. At 225 n.2
- Ferrua, A 1989. *Note e giunte alle iscrizioni cristiane antiche della Sicilia*. Vatican. At 123-124 no.471
- Manganaro, G. 1994. *Per una storia della 'chora Katanaia'*. In Olshausen, E., Sonnabend, H.(eds.), *Stuttgarter Kolloquium zur historischen Geographie des Altertums 4 (1990) / Geographica Historica 7*. Herausgegeben von Ernst Kirsten.. Amsterdam: Verlag Adolf M. Hakkert. pp. 127-174. At 174 n.175

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-09-10): ISic4427. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4022747>